

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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ADVANCE CARE PLANNING IN A SKILLED NURSING FACILITY:
A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

An increasing number of deaths in the United States are taking place in post-acute and skilled nursing facilities (SNF) and the trend is expected to continue. Demand for higher quality care at the end-of-life (EoL) calls for improvements in bedside nursing related to palliative care (PC) including advance care planning (ACP). In the state of California, a centerpiece of ACP is the completion of the Physician's Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST) form.

The purpose of the project was to improve ACP activities in a large post-acute care facility located in Southern California. The aims were (1) to describe the current state of ACP practices, (2) to develop and implement a PC-centered training program for licensed and non-licensed nurses, and (3) to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention on ACP.

The project employed an observational pre-posttest design. Nurses (licensed and non-licensed) were provided a class on PC concepts including EoL care and documentation. A tool modified from the literature measured PC and ACP knowledge, skills and attitudes (KSA) of nurses (28 items, Likert scale, range 1-5). Pre-post-intervention chart audits evaluated POLST completeness.

POLST forms from patient's charts ($n = 60$), licensed registered nurses ($n = 10$), licensed vocational nurses ($n = 26$), and non-licensed clinical nursing assistants ($n = 50$) comprised the sample for this project. Post-intervention chart audits for POLST completeness increased from 52% to 62% (a 10-percentage point increase). Licensed nurses and unlicensed CNA's post-test mean scores on PC knowledge, skills and attitudes improved (mean 3.71 [SD .43] to mean 4.17 [SD .49], mean 3.76 [SD .65] to mean 3.90

[SD .70], respectively). In addition, aggregated post-test scores for both groups improved (3.74 [1-5, SD .57] to 4.02 [1-5, SD .63], $t = 5.63$, $p = < .001$). Twenty-two percent ($n = 19$) of the participants showed marginal KSA decrements (range differences -1.11 to -0.04).

Implementation of PC-based trainings improves nursing KSA related to palliative and EoL care across nursing levels. PC trainings may improve completeness of POLST documentation. The decrements in KSA scores suggest that trainings may sensitize nurses to challenges in providing palliative and EoL care. This project demonstrates the feasibility of implementing a facility wide PC educational program to a population who frequently lack access to evidence-based PC and EoL information.

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BACKGROUND

Although there has been an increased interest in improving advance care planning (ACP) over the last few decades, the topic is poorly understood by the general public (Silveira, DiPiero, Gerrity, & Feudtner, 2000). A small, unpublished survey conducted by an internist writing in the *Journal of the American Medical Association (JAMA)* suggested that, when queried, only two in ten of her patients understood what ACP was (Tinetti, 2012). Several factors may play into this, including dated reimbursement mechanisms and a medical culture that has, until very recently, encouraged continuous and often aggressive treatments from birth to the final few months of life. Incessant politicization of the healthcare system by elected officials, policy makers and media outlets likely contribute to this knowledge deficit (for a current example, consider the characterization of ACP reimbursement discussions by some in Washington D.C. as “death panels”) (Rutenberg & Calmes, 2009).

The United States congress moved us into a new era for ACP with the passage of the Patient Self-Determination Act (PSDA) in 1991. The Act encouraged patients and families to participate in joint decision-making activities with their providers, including goals of care (GoC) and end-of-life (EoL) discussions. The legislation effectively rebranded American healthcare from a fully opaque, hierarchical and top-down system to a consumer-driven, “patient-centered” healthcare model with opportunities for patients and families to participate in all aspects of care (Teno et al., 1997). Further driving these ideas is a pervasive belief that by increasing ACP, late life experiences may be improved (Dying in America, 2015; Sopcheck, 2016; Lazenby, Ercolano, Schulman-Green, & McCorkle, 2012).

Problem Statement

Americans today are living longer but with more chronic, life-limiting diseases, such as dementia, diabetes and congestive heart failure (Ji, 2016). This has created an increased burden on patients, families, and the healthcare system (Center for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2012). In fact, 50% of Medicare dollars are used by 5% of Medicare recipients (Joynt, Gawande, Orav, & Jha, 2013), most of which is spent in the last few months of life (Zhang et al., 2009). Evidence suggests that these expenditures do not translate into improved late life experiences. In a discouraging study by Singer, Lynn, Teno, Lunney, Meeker, & Lorenz (2014), symptom burden *actually increased* across disease states in the last decade. One response to these disturbing trends has been a push by nursing and other healthcare thought leaders to more effectively focus on care that is consistent with patient and family preferences (Unroe, Hickman, & Torke, 2016). A similar push that is gaining more traction is for evidence-based treatments that improving quality of life (QoL) (Singer et al., 2016). The development and rapid implementation of the Physician Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST) form is further evidence of a widespread attempt to improve care at the EoL by standardizing the documentation of patient care preferences (Wenger et al., 2013). Discussions of preferences are increasingly important in skilled nursing facilities (SNFs) as upwards of 29% of all deaths in the United States occur in this setting – and it is expected to increase to almost 40% by 2025 (CDC, 2014).

While broad uptake of ACP has seen positive gains over the last decade, arriving at specific care preferences that are durable across care settings has been problematic (Yung, Walling, Min, Wenger, & Ganz, 2010). Large numbers of patients admitted to

the SNFs continue to present with little or no documentation of care preferences (e.g., cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) or placement of a feeding tube) (Van Leuven, 2012). Moreover, the job of educating patients and families about ACP in these settings often falls on registered nurses (RNs), licensed vocational nurses (LVNs), and, potentially, even clinical nursing assistants (CNAs) working at the front-lines of care. Unfortunately, many of these individuals have limited education on these topics (Kelly, Thrane, Virani, Malloy, & Ferrell, 2011) which may lead to less optimal ACP implementation and untoward outcomes.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to improve ACP in the post-acute, SNF-based population. The specific aims of the project are fourfold: one, to describe current ACP activities in the SNF setting; two, to develop an education program targeted at bedside staff to support these efforts; three, to implement the educational program; and four, to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention.

Supporting Framework

Evidence-based practice models and frameworks are necessary to help guide translation of research into real-world clinical practice settings (Schaffer, Sandau, & Diedrick, 2013). Quality Improvement (QI) models are equally necessary because they serve as organizing mechanisms that allow stakeholders to focus on a problem and systematically arrive at a solution or practice change that will result in a better product or outcome (Associates in Process Improvement, 2016; Brewer, Verran, & Stichler, 2008; Oh, Toh, & Seng-Giap, 2011). The framework chosen for this project is the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) learning cycle (see Figure 1). Developed by the chief architect of the

QI movement, Walter Shewhart, the PDSA model is a widely cited ‘quality management’ tool that was originally designed to reduce variations in the production and delivery of goods and services. Shewhart’s central thesis - as relevant today for the healthcare industry as it was for American manufacturing more than seventy-five years ago - is that a constant, never-ending evaluation and assessment of management policies and procedures will lead to a culture of continuous process improvement and, by extension, better products or outcomes (Best & Neuhauser, 2006).

The PDSA QI model identifies four stages:

- Plan – identify the problem and figure out what changes are needed to fix it
- Do – implement the change or intervention
- Study – measure and analyze process outcomes
- Act – evaluate, take stock and ask the question, “Does the process change or intervention result in measurable improvement?”

According to Shewhart, the “Plan” stage should include an outline of objectives that clearly delineate a course for change. This can be done by first defining existing conditions, then posing a change idea, and finally planning for the change to be tested or implemented. For the current DNP project, the Plan was to engage stakeholders in identifying the problem of incomplete or inaccurate POLST forms and to develop baseline data related to ACP practices in a large, stand-alone post-acute, skilled nursing facility (“Sunnyside”). This was done through two separate steps (a) resident chart reviews to assess for POLST form status and (b) pre-testing for licensed nursing and CNA staff to assess current levels of EoL experiences, attitudes and care preferences documentation/ POLST form knowledge. The pre-testing survey tool focused on whether staff possessed the skills necessary to engage patients and families in EoL and GoC discussions.

Shewhart's "Do" stage requires specific strategies to carry out the proposed change and prepare it for launch. Process analyses are conducted and new tools and protocols are developed to foster improvements (Van Tiel et al., 2006). For this project, an ACP education program was created and implemented for front-line clinical staff. The program was divided into two parts or groups. The first was for licensed staff, such as RNs and LVNs, and the second was for non-licensed CNA staff.

For the "Study" stage of the model, before and after intervention implementation variables are measured and data evaluated and stakeholders reflect on the "iterative" and continuous improvement process. For this DNP project, an education program post-test was done with the goal of measuring new knowledge and content acquisition related to GoC, EoL and POSLT form documentation and other related ACP activities.

Finally, for the "Act" stage of the model, Shewhart suggests that stakeholders record the positive process changes that yield improvements and begin to standardize these across all levels of service (Barlog & Ginn, 1994). For the current project, the question asked, "Have ACP activities improved?" This was done through a post-intervention chart audit to assess whether greater numbers of completed and signed POLST forms were evident in patients' charts. Recommendations and a reflective "lessons learned" summary document was generated and submitted to stakeholders for review. Questions included:

- Has the change added more costs?
- Were mistakes made?
- Has overall performance related to ACP activities improved?
- What could have been done differently?

- How can we further enhance process flow and front-line staff education in ways that optimize quality indicators and improve patient outcomes?

Stakeholders

Identification of stakeholders is an important component to a QI project. The prevailing question could be stated as follows: “Why should stakeholders want to invest valuable resources and time into supporting a one-time and later iterative ACP education intervention?” Through implementation of the current DNP project, the author hoped to show that improvements in ACP were realized and that patients and families benefited. Key stakeholders included DaVita Medical Group/ Healthcare Partners (DMG) and Sunnyside Nursing Center, doing business as FH & HF, LLC. Nursing and CNA staff were also be considered to be stakeholders.

Figure 1. Conceptual model: PDSA cycle for quality improvement. Adapted from Best & Neubauer, 2006.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Institute of Medicine (IOM) identifies and recognizes ample evidence for the need to improve care at the EoL (*Dying in America: Improving Quality and Honoring Individual Preferences Near the End of Life*, 2015). Beginning in the 1990s, the numbers of high-quality, evidence-based studies that support these trends continues to grow. The purpose of this literature review is to highlight the evidence related to ACP efforts, POLST documentation, practice change dynamics and the need to educate healthcare nursing staff in these areas. The DNP project's specific purpose was to improve ACP efforts in post-acute, SNF-based populations with the aims of describing current ACP practices, developing a POLST-centered educational program for nurses working at all license levels, evaluating the effectiveness of the program, and reflecting and commenting on the practice change process. The review of literature is organized around three central themes: ACP and POLST; practice change; and the adult learner.

The databases included in this review were PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. General search topics included POLST documentation, ACP and practice change, and adult learner. The search terms included were "POLST and MOLST" (266 records; PubMed, CINAHL), "adult learner" (895 records; PubMed, CINAHL), and "practice change" (50279; PubMed). To narrow the searches, the terms "POLST" (94 records; PubMed), "POLST and decision-making" (20 records; PubMed, CINAHL), "MOLST and POLST and decision-making" (2 records; PubMed, CINAHL), "adult learner nursing" (205 records; PubMed, CINAHL), "adult learner and nursing education" (5 records; PubMed, CINAHL), and "practice change education skilled nursing facility" (15 records; PubMed, CINAHL) were used. Limitations included English only scholarly

journals with publication dates of no more than 10 years. Journals that addressed issues specific to ACP, EoL, GoC, palliative care, healthcare policy, and adult education were included, whereas publications with a focus strictly on medical ethics and electronic health records were excluded. For this initial literature review, a total of 17 articles were identified.

Advance Care Planning and POLST Documentation

Several themes arise in the literature when considering ACP and POLST documentation, including advancing patient-centered care, addressing perceived barriers in communication, addressing knowledge gaps, improving decision-making quality, and reducing discord between patients' stated care preferences, what is documented in the chart, and the care that they actually receive. The majority of studies reviewed support the notion that the post-acute setting, owing primarily to its older patient population and high prevalence of ACP concerns, is particularly challenged in these areas. To exemplify the point, in their 2015 systematic review on POLST form use, Hickman, Keevern, and Hammes found that almost half of the research studies (11 out of 23) were conducted in post-acute, SNF-based populations. The data are clear that increases in ACP activity across all settings is suggestive of the need for better EoL care and more accurate and durable documentation methods (Schmidt, Hickman, Tolle, & Brooks, 2004; Hickman, Tolle, Brummel-Smith, & Carley, 2004; Hickman et al, 2017).

Broadly defined, ACP is a method of understanding current health status by identifying and describing health goals and care preferences throughout the lifespan but with special emphasis at the onset of incurable disease or at EoL. Included in this definition is the designation of a proxy decision-maker, often a family member, who

agrees to make health-related decisions on behalf of the patient and execute on stated and documented GoC wishes. Until the early 1990s, advance directives (ADs) were the main means for conveying these wishes, but research has shown that their usability and portability, both inside and outside the hospital setting, can be ill-defined and ineffective, often resulting in unwanted care (Dunn, Schmidt, Carley, Donius, Weinstein, & Dull, 1996; Mirarchi, Kalantzis, Hunter, McCracken, & Kisiel, 2009; Wenger et al., 2013; Amro, Ramasamy, Strom, Weiner, & Jaber, 2016).

POLST form documentation began in the early 1990s in Oregon when a working group of physicians, ethicists, and long-term care advocates came together and created a simplified form designed to define care preferences that would be fully portable across all HC settings (Tolle, Tilden, Nelson, & Dunn, 1998). The idea took hold and soon spread to other regions of the country and by 2004 a national 'POLST paradigm taskforce' had been formed. Today, most states have operationalized the POLST paradigm or have an equivalent system, for example, in Massachusetts, the MOLST form (Medical Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment) is used rather than the POLST form (Schmidt, Zive, Fromme, Cook, & Tolle, 2014). As of January 1, 2016, Nurse Practitioners and Physician Assistants can sign the POLST form in California. Sixteen other states have enacted similar legislation.

Increases in documentation activity, however, do not necessarily equate to greater numbers of high quality completed POLST forms or better EoL care. Hickman et al. (2009), for example, in their telephone survey study looking at POLST use in the hospice setting, found that incomplete POLST orders can lead to unwanted treatments or hospitalizations and, by extension, reduced QoC (for an earlier discussion on this topic

related to hospitalized patients, see Lee, Brummel-Smith, Meyer, Drew, & London, 2000). Hickman et al. (2009) and Beach and Morrison (2002) argue that do-not-resuscitate (DNR) orders, which apply to the critical time period between marked physical decline and just prior to death, are defined as abstaining from enacting CPR, but *may not apply* to the withholding of other treatments, for example, the initiation of intravenous fluid resuscitation or abdominal paracentesis to drain fluid for ease of breathing or the cessation of pain. The author suggests that individuation of the form is a necessary component and that an over emphasis of the DNR order on the POLST form may cause simplification of treatment options. In an earlier study looking at hospice patients who were DNR, Hickman et al. (2004) found that 78% of POLST forms had some measure of orders for higher levels of care, such as requests for transfer to the hospital or placement of feeding tubes. There is debate as to whether these more aggressive treatment selections are the result of miscommunication or a lack of staff education related to POLST but also basic palliative care principles. Clinical staff may find it a challenge to disentangle the more subtle meanings and treatment options encapsulated in the POLST form (Clemency, Cordes, Lindstrom, Basior, & Waldrop, 2017).

The evidence suggests that myriad factors contribute to the apparent confusion surrounding POLST orders and resultant ACP discussions that clinicians may have with patients and families. Misunderstandings related to EoL concepts and palliative care principles may be key factors, but also complicit is the structure of the one-page POLST form with its three main “sections” and their effect on clinicians’ confidence and attitudes when documenting EoL preferences. While a seemingly simple, easy-to-complete

document, Hickman et al. (2015), in their systemic review looking at over two dozen high-level evidence studies, noted that POLST orders showed a high degree of individuation and was reflected in the finding that 35 out of a possible 36 order combinations were identified. Hickman et al. (2009) and Sugiyama et al. (2013), in their respective prospective survey studies, found that, when assessing for HC worker attitudes and clinician experiences related to the POLST form in both hospice and acute inpatient settings, a majority complained of a lack of time and inadequate education and training. McGough, Hauschildt, Mollon, and Fields (2015) found that when nurses are provided with *recurring, mandatory* education on POLST practices, their knowledge and comfort levels increase (6.7% pre-education to 37.5% post-education; $p < .006$). The author notes that the number of completed forms also increased. Results from these studies point to the benefits of ACP education and training for bedside nursing staff.

Quality, stability and consistency of POLST orders, provider confidence in conducting ACP discussions, and decision-making activities also show prominently in the literature. Vo and colleagues (2011) conducted an anonymous survey looking at HC worker age, years of experience and low-prevalence (LP) versus high-prevalence (HP) use of MOLST forms in SNFs. The researchers found that the quality of care that residents received was directly proportional to form usage. Moreover, the author found that HP facilities showed higher perceived satisfaction scores in symptom management, including pain control. In fact, over 46% of surveyed respondents agreed that patients with completed MOLST forms had better pain management than those who did not (LP facility response was 11.8%; $p < .0001$). For the current QI project, the author hypothesizes that licensed and unlicensed bedside staff knowledge and levels of

interactive experience and palliative care-related trainings offered directly influence the quality of EoL care and the types and kinds of information and education about GoC that patients and families actually receive.

Lastly, Hickman et al. (2017) and Heyland et al. (2013) highlight issues related to QoC, discord in POLST orders, patient treatment preferences, and decision-making experiences. In a pilot study using chart abstractions and interviews with nursing home (NH) patients and surrogates ($n = 28$), Hickman et al. found that initial discord between POLST orders and current care preferences were moderate to high (79% of residents and 50% of surrogates; $p = .24$). After discussion and clarification these numbers decreased to 29%, respectively. The author notes that, when queried, the top reasons for the discrepancies were lack of knowledge and lack of clarity with respect to orders listed on the POLST form. According to the researchers, these data suggest that there are potential problems with the initial conversation and execution of the form and that *periodic reevaluations* of POLST orders and care preferences are warranted. Heyland et al., in their hospital-based prospective study, looked at changes in expressed versus documented care preferences among all active parties prior to and after a hospital admission. The author found that agreement between expressed wishes and those documented in the chart was a low 30.2%. The author suggests that gaps in communication and lack of a full exploration surrounding documented EoL preferences result in discord and served to place patients at risk for receiving unwanted treatments (this idea is often referred to in the literature as the “error of omission”).

Evidence-based practice change fundamentals include understanding the problem, developing a solution, engaging stakeholders, securing administrative and managerial

support, drafting a measurement plan, creating a timeline, developing a budget, and reviewing and reflecting on the completed project (Gallagher-Ford, Fineout-Overholt, Stillwell, & Mazurek-Melnyk, 2011). The evidence suggests that applied practice change science is as effective in healthcare settings as it is in many other areas of service and commerce.

Morrison, Chichin, Carter, Burack, Lantz, & Meier (2005) conducted a controlled trial related to ACP efforts in nursing home residents and showed that a structured, multicomponent training and reflection intervention module for social workers significantly increased the numbers of complete and signed POLST forms (documentation of preferences for intervention group versus control group: CPR 40% versus 20%; $p = .005$; artificial nutrition and hydration 47% versus 9%; $p < .010$; intravenous antibiotics 44% versus 9%; $p < .010$; and hospitalization 49% versus 16%; $p < .010$). An equally significant finding in this study was that those in the non-intervention control group were more likely than the intervention group to receive treatments discordant with prior stated wishes. These results lend further weight to the idea that interventions that change patient outcomes by changing practice with respect to ACP activities are indicated.

ACP and POLST documentation activities in the sub-acute, SNF-based setting can be complex and often confusing. However, as many of the studies in this review of literature suggest, opportunities exist—and the need is repeatedly justified—for QI projects that address staff education and training. Specifically, many investigators state that these efforts should focus on a deeper understanding about patient care preferences as they relate to treatment options on the POLST form itself. Many also suggest that they

should include initiation of ‘meaningful’ EoL discussions which will result in more accurate documentation of POLST forms. Finally, several researchers intimated that practice change considerations should be reflected at increased rates in the clinical education curriculum. Commitments to patient-centered care along with requirements for measurable increases in QoL indices and patient outcomes will continue to drive ACP QI efforts forward.

Adult Learner

To successfully implement this DNP project, consideration was given to the adult learner. A palliative care-centered curriculum was developed for licensed nurses and unlicensed CNAs working in the post-acute and long-term care setting. It was assumed that the nursing staff’s time is highly impacted and that the educational training program would have to be done using the in-service format and offered before, during or immediately following the healthcare worker’s shift. This suggests that time constraints and patient care stressors will continue to be a potential barrier to learning.

Baile & Blatner (2014), in their descriptive study laying out a pedagogy designed for medical students, suggest that using an experiential simulation-role play-reflection type curriculum may be the most appropriate in time-pressed groups, such as medical and nursing students and HC workers. Methods in this system include warm-ups, role-creation and role-reversal, each with the expressed intention of developing insight into the masked attitudes, thoughts and feelings of others. The author’s describe an applied communication system they call SPIKES (Setting, Perception, Invitation, Knowledge, Emotions, Strategy, and Summary), which is used to break bad news to patients and families. The authors note that the system follows lock-step with newer adult learning

theories. For our purposes, however, the breaking bad news portion was reformatted to follow an open-ended and question-and-response format.

Braun, Cheang, and Shigeta (2005) describe a study using nonexperimental design with 106 attendees enrolled in an education module for direct care HC workers, including unlicensed nurse aide staff. The goals of the program were to teach the basics of the aging process, including assessment, reporting skills, cultivation of empathy for elderly populations, self-care, and stress management strategies. Additionally, the study set out to validate the important contributions that direct care workers and ‘paraprofessionals’ make in the lives of seniors. Of the six 4-hour-long modules, highlights included topics on death and dying. The author’s note that, according to post-module surveys, emancipatory learning approaches were a strength of the educational program. In other words, participants were encouraged to “tell their story” (p. 119). By doing this, it was noted, participants were able to make meaning out of personal experience. Similar to Baile and Blatner’s (2014) SPIKES communication regime, the authors offer a comparable approach that allows for expressions of intuition, feelings, sensing, imagining, and, what they refer to as ‘cognitive knowing’. Eight-one pre- and post-test surveys suggested that participants found that the program was helpful in knowing the aging process (pre-test score 14.84, post-test score 18.04; $p = .000$).

Nursing education is a well-researched area and figures prominently in the literature. However, there appears to be a dearth of research looking at education theory and curriculum development for non-licensed CNAs. Barriers lending credence to this deficit include reluctance or inability for CNAs to get time away from work duties, programmatic costs, perceived reluctance to participate in didactic learning activities, and

a work culture that does not always value unlicensed bedside care workers. The fact remains that over 80% of paid long-term care workers in the United States fall into this category (Noelker, 2001) and trends are expected to grow as the population ages.

Patients and families may benefit the most from ACP education and training for nurses, paraprofessionals, and CNA staff, the author concludes.

METHODS

The purpose of this doctoral project was to improve ACP activities with a focus on POLST form documentation and GoC discussions in a post-acute care/ skilled nursing facility (SNF). The following sections describes in detail the project's setting, sample, measures, procedures, ethical issues, and evaluation plan.

Setting

The setting for the DNP quality improvement (QI) project was a large, stand-alone 418-bed post-acute/ SNF located in the greater Los Angeles metropolitan region (referred to as "the SNF"). Two-thirds of the beds were skilled or custodial and one-third were assisted living residents. All beds were Medi-Cal and Medicare certified. The SNF is owned by a privately held, non-profit California corporation. Of the 330 full-time, part-time and per diem staff members, 180 are nurses (licensed RNs or LVNs and unlicensed clinical nursing assistants (CNAs)). The SNF employs one full-time staff nurse educator and maintains a contract with an online clinical nursing education vendor. Educational in-services covering a myriad of topics including end-of-life (EoL) care are conducted throughout the calendar year. Currently, only licensed nurses are eligible to attend these in-services.

Sample

There were two sample populations for this project. The first sample included sixty facility patients' charts ($n = 60$). Thirty patient charts were audited for POLST presence and completeness prior to the educational intervention (September/ October 2017), and 30 patient charts were audited for POLST presence and completeness post-

intervention (October/ November 2017). There were no direct contacts between the author and those patients whose charts were audited.

The second sample consisted of facility-employed licensed nurses and CNAs (full-time, part-time and per diem). Staffing mix was as ethnically diverse as the patient and resident population. Approximately 180 licensed nurses and non-licensed CNAs were employed by the facility. Licensed staff included RNs and LVNs. Unlicensed staff included all bedside CNAs. The latter group has extended daily patient contact related to feedings, bathing, toileting, and personal assistance activities. Both licensed nurses and non-licensed CNAs comprised the sample that received the educational intervention ($n = 86$) and completed the EoL Professional Caregiver Survey (referred to here as the KSA survey).

Measures

Outcome measures for this project include 1) a POLST completeness tool for chart audits that was created by the author and included clinical and demographic variables (see Appendix A), and 2) the KSA survey for the nurses and CNAs (see Appendix B). The POLST form includes 31 individual items which were coded as present/ absent (1/ 0). Examples of POLST items include, “Medical Interventions [select one]: 1) Full Treatment, 2) Selective Treatment, or 3) Comfort-Focused Treatment” and “Information and Signatures: Discussed with 1) Patient or 2) Legally Recognized Decision-Maker.” The presence or absence of the form on the chart was also coded 1 or 0. A summative score was generated for each POLST (range 0-32).

The KSA survey (Lazenby et al., 2012) included demographic variables and was designed for palliative and EoL care clinicians to measure knowledge, skills and

attitudes. Example questions include, “I am comfortable talking to patients and families about personal choice and self-determination,” and “I am familiar with the services hospice provides,” and “I am comfortable dealing with ethical issues related to EoL/ hospice/ palliative care.” The KSA tool includes 28 Likert scale questions (“Strongly Agree” to “Strongly Disagree”; range 1-5) and are categorized into 3 subscales: Patient-and-Family-Centered Communication (PFCC; 12-questions), Culture and Ethical Values (CEV; 8-questions), and Effective Care Delivery (ECD; 8-questions). Minor changes in wording were made to questions specific to the unlicensed group (e.g. questions 4, 9, 11, 21, 25, and 26) to reflect clinical focus and scope of practice. For example, in question 26, which relates to assisted suicide, the language was changed from ‘addressing requests for assisted suicide’ to ‘discussing assisted suicide’ since CNAs are not allowed to initiate changes to care plans nor are they allowed to request or suggest changes in clinician orders.

Current Facility Procedures Related to POLST

A licensed staff nurse (RN) or a social worker (SW) typically completes the POLST form within 72 hours of transfer from an acute setting or upon direct admission from home or the community. POLST forms are bright pink-colored 8 x 11 double-sided high-gauge stock sheets of paper that are portable and transferrable between care settings, including the home or community. Generally, SWs teach licensed staff about the POLST form, ACP, and basic PC principles through periodic in-service trainings conducted at the SNF. It is worth reiterating that, as of this writing, only licensed nursing staff may be required to attend the palliative care/ EoL in-service trainings.

Project Procedures

The current project involved pre-and-post-intervention chart reviews with POLST data abstraction and the initiation of a palliative care-focused educational in-service for licensed nurses and non-licensed CNAs. Project procedures were as follows:

Chart Abstraction

The author performed chart reviews to assess POLST form completeness. Pre-chart audits ($n = 30$) were performed from September 27th through October 14th, 2017 and post-chart audits ($n = 30$) were performed from October 27th through November 12th, 2017. The pre-chart audits were performed two days prior to the start of the educational intervention. The post-chart audits were performed within 72 hours of admission. The two-week period between chart audits comprised the implementation phase of the project.

Educational In-service Intervention

1. Once approved by the facility's Administrator and the California State University, Long Beach (CSULB) Institutional Review Board (IRB), licensed nursing staff were invited to join one of 4 palliative care educational training in-services (PCT). The PCTs were offered through staff huddles and bimonthly meetings and by the posting of flyers in the staff lunchroom and on the employee information board. Overhead announcements were made 30-minutes prior to the start of each scheduled in-service.
2. PCTs for the licensed groups were voluntary. Four one-hour trainings were conducted. The PCT for the unlicensed CNA group was slotted into their normally scheduled and facility-mandated in-service trainings having to do with various topics. The researcher was allotted six 30-minute in-service training slots for the CNAs. Often, these trainings ran overtime and were actually 45-minutes. The SNF's education coordinator rearranged previously scheduled trainings covering other non-licensed clinical staff topics in order to accommodate the PCT.
3. In-service trainings for the unlicensed group took place from October 16th through October 19, 2017. PCTs for the licensed group took place between October 20th and October 26, 2017.
4. All PCTs were conducted at the facilities' designated in-house classroom location.

5. All licensed and unlicensed participants were apprised of the volunteer nature of the PCT (except CNAs for whom the courses were mandatory) and the consent to participate in the project. All participants, including CNAs, were apprised of the voluntary nature of the consent to participate and completion of the pre-post surveys.
6. All course participants who successfully completed the pre-course consent forms and the pre-post-test surveys did so using the pencil-and-paper format. None chose to use the online Qualtrics survey option, which was thoroughly explained. For the consent form, participants placed these in a pre-labeled manila envelope titled "CONSENT FORM" that was placed at the front of the classroom at each of the PCTs. For the pre-post surveys, participants placed these in separately labelled manila envelopes titled "PRE-COURSE SURVEY" and "POST-COURSE SURVEY," respectively. These were also placed at the front of the classroom for each of the PCTs. All consent forms and surveys were anonymous and included only a numeric identifier.
7. Pre-and-post surveys were matched using a five-digit unique identifier for pairing and analysis. Participants were asked to use the last 5-digits of their cell phone number as the numeric identifier. All participants produced a cell number identifier. Each one of the paper-and-pencil pre-post surveys were uploaded by hand into Qualtrics by the author.
8. Hard copies of the paper-and-pencil completed consent forms and pre-post surveys are currently being kept in a locked desk drawer in a locked office. This will be done for the required three-year safe-storage period.
9. A PC principles focused education curriculum was developed for nurses and CNAs. The intension was to design and implement a curriculum that would serve to increase knowledge, skills and attitudes related to PC and ACP activities. Areas of focus included PC, hospice, POLST form, EoL care, and GoC specific to post-acute/ SNF-based patient populations. Licensed and unlicensed nurses were provided essentially the same curricular content though content was adjusted to accommodate time constraints.
10. Licensed and unlicensed staff received separate PCTs as prior research has shown that nurses and nursing assistants share unique perceptions of experience (Lancaster, Kolakowsky-Hayner, Kovacich, & Greer-Williams, 2015).
11. Curriculum was developed from existing online and classroom-based sources including educational materials from End-of-Life Nursing Education Consortium (ELNEC; www.aacnnursing.org), the California Compassionate Care Coalition (CCCC; www.coalitionccc.org), the California State University Institute for Palliative Care (csupalliativecare.org), Center to Advance Palliative Care (CAPC; www.capc.org); California POLST Project (CAPOLST; www.capolst.org), and Familias en Accion

(www.familiaenaccion.org). All copyrighted and permission-to-use pathways were followed and have been documented.

12. A mixed-method teaching approach was employed. These included didactic discussion, definition of terms, small group breakout sessions, and whole group shared experience sessions dubbed by the author as “Free Speech” exercises. For this exercise, participants were provided a voluntary opportunity to select at random a 3x5 index card and to share their thoughts or experiences by reflecting on the question or statement that was penned on the card. For example, one card asked, “How do you like to be present with dying patients?”
13. Incentives were offered at each of the PCTs and included raffles for \$10 Target gift cards. Coffee and snack foods were served.

Ethical Issues

The facility administrator provided a letter of support (see Appendix C). California State University, Long Beach’s IRB approval was obtained prior to the initiation of the project (see Appendix D). Patients were not tracked, approached or affected in any way as a result of this project. Patient charts were not removed from the facility nor were any contents photocopied. All Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) and privacy requirements were carefully followed and documented. Storage of all research materials are being handled per IRB rules as previously described.

Analysis and Evaluation Plan

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package Social Sciences (“SPSS”) version 24 and an online statistical software program called Intellectus Statistics (<https://analyze.intellectusstatistics.com>). The Intellectus Statistics program was used concurrently on request of the University to test the usability and effectiveness of the online application. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) and measures of central tendency (mean, range) and dispersion (standard deviation) were used to describe

sample characteristics. Paired *t*-tests (*t*-statistic and *p*-value) were used to examine for differences for the total sample pre- and post-educational program and between the sample groups pre- and post-educational intervention. Two metrics (percentages) were generated comparing POLST completeness pre- and post-educational intervention.

Metric 1. Percentage (%) of POLST **Items** Completed per Form

Numerator = Total Number of POLST Items Completed per Form

Denominator = Total Number of POLST Items

Metric 2. Percentage (%) of POLST Forms with **all Items** Completed

Numerator = Total Number of POLST Forms with Complete Data

Denominator = Total Number of POLST Forms

RESULTS

Related to the palliative care educational intervention, 92 of 180 eligible clinical staff (51%) consented to participate in the palliative care in-service training (PCT). Complete data for analysis were available for 86 nurses (licensed nurses $n = 36$ [43%] and unlicensed CNAs $n = 50$ [57%]). The licensed group included 10 registered nurses (RNs) and 26 licensed vocational nurses (LVNs). Participants' demographic and job related information such as age, ethnicity, years worked in the SNF setting, highest level of education, whether they had completed an advance directive and received EoL training in the past are described in Table 1.

Average age of participants was 39 years (range 24-70, SD 13). Gender was 87% female and 13% male. Ethnicity was diverse: Filipinos were the most represented group ($n = 25$ [29%]); Black/ African American and Hispanic/ Latino tied for the second most represented groups ($n = 22$ [25%] both groups); Asian/ Pacific Islander and White/ Caucasian were the least represented groups in the sample ($n = 11$ [13%] and $n = 5$ [6%], respectively). The remaining sample declined to state ($n = 1$ [1%]). Most of the participants held vocational degrees ($n = 42$ [49%]) followed by Bachelor's degrees and Associate's degrees ($n = 19$ [22%] and $n = 11$ [13%], respectively) with the remaining sample declining to state ($n = 3$ [3%]). Years of work experience in the post-acute/ SNF setting for both groups ranged from just under 1 year to 37 years (mean 8, SD 7.9). Forty-one participants said that they had had EoL training, 29 said that they had not and 16 were unsure (48%, 34% and 18%, respectively).

Table 1

Sample Characteristics

	Total (<i>n</i> = 86)	Licensed RN/LVN (<i>n</i> = 36)	Non-Licensed CNA (<i>n</i> = 50)
Gender			
Male	<i>n</i> = 11 (13%)	<i>n</i> = 4 (11%)	<i>n</i> = 7 (14%)
Female	<i>n</i> = 75 (87%)	<i>n</i> = 32 (89%)	<i>n</i> = 43 (86%)
Race			
Black/ African American	<i>n</i> = 22 (25%)	<i>n</i> = 3 (8%)	<i>n</i> = 19 (38%)
White/ Caucasian	<i>n</i> = 5 (6%)	<i>n</i> = 4 (11%)	<i>n</i> = 1 (2%)
Filipino	<i>n</i> = 25 (29%)	<i>n</i> = 18 (50%)	<i>n</i> = 7 (14%)
Hispanic/ Latino	<i>n</i> = 22 (26%)	<i>n</i> = 6 (17%)	<i>n</i> = 16 (32%)
Asian/ Pacific Islander	<i>n</i> = 11 (13%)	<i>n</i> = 5 (14%)	<i>n</i> = 6 (12%)
Decline to State	<i>n</i> = 1 (1%)	<i>n</i> = 0 (0%)	<i>n</i> = 1 (2%)
Highest level of education			
High school/ GED	<i>n</i> = 11 (13%)	<i>n</i> = 0 (0%)	<i>n</i> = 11 (22%)
Vocational/ Certificate	<i>n</i> = 42 (49%)	<i>n</i> = 16 (44%)	<i>n</i> = 26 (52%)
Associate's Degree	<i>n</i> = 11 (13%)	<i>n</i> = 7 (20%)	<i>n</i> = 4 (8%)
Bachelor's Degree	<i>n</i> = 19 (22%)	<i>n</i> = 12 (33%)	<i>n</i> = 7 (14%)
Decline to State	<i>n</i> = 3 (3%)	<i>n</i> = 1 (3%)	<i>n</i> = 2 (4%)
Number of years worked in post-acute/ SNF setting?			
Mean (Range, <i>SD</i>) in years	8 (1-37, 7.9)	6 (SD 4.7)	10 (SD 9.2)
Have you ever had advanced care planning/ end-of-life training?			
Yes	<i>n</i> = 41 (48%)	<i>n</i> = 17 (47%)	<i>n</i> = 24 (48%)
No	<i>n</i> = 29 (34%)	<i>n</i> = 12 (33%)	<i>n</i> = 17 (34%)
Not Sure	<i>n</i> = 16 (18%)	<i>n</i> = 7 (20%)	<i>n</i> = 9 (18%)
Do you personally have an advanced directive?			
Yes	<i>n</i> = 20 (23%)	<i>n</i> = 6 (17%)	<i>n</i> = 14 (28%)
No	<i>n</i> = 58 (68%)	<i>n</i> = 29 (80%)	<i>n</i> = 29 (58%)
Not Sure	<i>n</i> = 8 (9%)	<i>n</i> = 1 (3%)	<i>n</i> = 7 (14%)

Results Specific to the Palliative Care Educational Intervention

Licensed nurses and non-licensed CNAs had similar levels of PC KSA at baseline (mean 3.71 vs. mean 3.76, t -statistic = $-.50$, $p = .619$). Knowledge skills and attitudes (KSA) related to advance care planning (ACP) and basic palliative care (PC) principles increased for both groups with education (licensed nurses 3.71 [1-5, SD .43] to 4.17 [1-5, SD .49]; unlicensed CNAs 3.76 [1-5, SD .65] to 3.90 [1-5, SD .70]; see Table 2). Licensed nurses' PC KSA mean scores improved more with education than their non-licensed colleagues (4.17 vs. 3.90, $t = 2.1$, $p = .043$). The total sample PC KSA scores improved with the educational intervention (3.74 [1-5, SD .57] to 4.02 [1-5, SD .63], $t = 5.63$, $p = < .001$; see Table 3).

The individual items of the questionnaire were examined by license status to identify response patterns among participants (see Tables 4 and 5). Differences by licensure and pre-post scoring were observed. As noted, the licensed group showed greater improvements in KSA than did the unlicensed group, but the differences between groups were minimal. Interestingly in 19 participants (22% of the total sample; 2 licensed and 17 non-licensed), post-test scores were actually lower than pre-test scores. Decrements were minimal (range differences -1.1 to -0.04 ; average decrease $-.31$ or a third of a point).

Table 2

RN/ LVN vs. CNA Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes Survey

Licensed vs. Non-Licensed	Pre-Test Mean (Range, SD)	Post-Test Mean (Range, SD)	<i>t</i> -test <i>p</i> -value
RN/ LVN <i>n</i> = 36	3.71 (1-5, .43)	4.17 (1-5, .49)	<i>t</i> = 8.69 <i>p</i> = .050
CNA <i>n</i> = 50	3.76 (1-5, .65)	3.90 (1-5, .70)	<i>t</i> = 2.42 <i>p</i> = .041

Table 3

Total Sample Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes Survey

Total Sample	Pre-Test (Mean, SD)	Post-Test (Mean, SD)	<i>t</i> -statistic <i>p</i> -value
RNs/ LVNs/ CNAs <i>n</i> = 86	3.74 (1-5, .57)	4.02 (1-5, .63)	<i>t</i> = 5.63 <i>p</i> < .001

Table 4

RN/ LVN Individual Questions Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes Survey

RN/ LVNs	Pre-Test Mean (Range, SD)	Post-Test Mean (Range, SD)	<i>p</i> -value
Q1: I am comfortable helping families to poor prognosis.	4.17 (2-5, .78)	4.26 (1-5, .70)	.521
Q2: I am able to set goals of care with patients and families.	3.97 (3-5, .65)	4.17 (3-5, .65)	.109
Q3: I am comfortable talking to patients and families about personal choice and self-determination.	4.06 (2-5, .79)	4.28 (2-5, .70)	.103
Q4: I am comfortable starting and participating in discussions about code status.	4.06 (3-5, .79)	4.11 (2-5, .78)	.661
Q5: I can assist family members and others through the grieving process.	3.56 (1-5, .78)	3.79 (1-5, .97)	.133
Q6: I am able to document the needs and interventions of my patients.	4.11 (3-5, .75)	4.31 (3-5, .62)	.051
Q7: I am comfortable talking with other health care professionals about the care of dying patients.	3.94 (1-5, .86)	4.17 (2-5, .77)	.103
Q8: I am comfortable helping to resolve difficult family conflicts about end-of-life care.	4.22 (3-5, .54)	4.36 (2-5, .64)	.230
Q9: I can recognize impending death (physiologic changes).	4.17 (3-5, .61)	4.42 (3-5, .60)	.048
Q10: I know how to use non-drug therapies in the management of patients' symptoms.	3.85 (1-5, 1.21)	4.23 (2-5, .85)	.040
Q11: I am able to address patients' and family members' fears of getting addicted to pain medications.	3.77 (1-5, .91)	4.17 (2-5, .82)	.004
Q12: I encourage patients and families to complete advance care planning.	4.00 (2-5, .83)	4.53 (2-5, .77)	<.001
Q13: I am comfortable dealing with ethical issues related to end-of-life/ hospice/ palliative care.	4.06 (2-5, .75)	3.83 (1-5, .91)	.044
Q14: I am able to deal with my feelings related to working with dying patients.	3.66 (1-5, .87)	3.91 (3-5, .92)	.083
Q15: I am able to be present with dying patients.	4.17 (3-5, .69)	4.42 (3-5, .69)	.059
Q16: I can address spiritual issues with patients and their families.	3.74 (1-5, .70)	4.14 (1-5, .81)	.003
Q17: I am comfortable dealing with patients' and families' religious and cultural perspectives.	4.08 (1-5, .81)	4.44 (3-5, .69)	.014
Q18: I am comfortable providing grief counseling for families.	3.50 (1-5, .91)	4.00 (2-5, .83)	<.001

RN/ LVNs	Pre-Test Mean (Range, SD)	Post-Test Mean (Range, SD)	<i>p</i> - value
Q19: I am comfortable providing grief counseling for staff.	3.61 (1-5, .87)	3.89 (2-5, .82)	.016
Q20: I am knowledgeable about cultural factors influencing end-of-life care.	3.38 (2-5, .92)	3.62 (2-5, .89)	.073
Q21: I can recognize when patients are appropriate for referral to hospice.	3.56 (1-5, .81)	4.17 (1-5, .91)	<.001
Q22: I am familiar with palliative care principles and national guidelines.	3.14 (1-5, .96)	4.14 (1-5, .90)	<.001
Q23: I am effective at helping patients and families navigate with health care system.	3.86 (2-5, .64)	4.42 (3-5, .65)	<.001
Q24: I am familiar with the services hospice provides.	2.76 (1-5, 1.27)	3.48 (1-5, 1.20)	.004
Q25: I am effective at helping to maintain continuity across care settings.	3.06 (1-5, .95)	3.79 (1-5, 1.07)	.002
Q26: I feel confident addressing requests for assisted suicide.	3.47 (2-5, .81)	4.03 (2-5, .81)	<.001
Q27: I have personal resources to help meet my needs when working with dying patients and their families.	3.69 (2-5, .75)	4.19 (3-5, .67)	.002
Q28: I feel that my workplace provides resources to support staff who care for dying patients.	3.50 (1-5, 1.06)	4.14 (1-5, 1.10)	<.001

Table 5

CNA Individual Questions Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes Survey

CNAs	Pre-Test Mean (Range, SD)	Post-Test Mean (Range, SD)	<i>p</i> -value
Q1: I am comfortable helping families to poor prognosis.	3.80 (2-5, .95)	4.21 (1-5, .89)	.004
Q2: I am able to set goals of care with patients and families.	4.22 (1-5, .86)	4.10 (1-5, .93)	.348
Q3: I am comfortable talking to patients and families about personal choice and self-determination.	3.98 (1-5, 1.03)	3.92 (2-5, 1.02)	.722
Q4: I am comfortable starting and participating in discussions about code status.	4.14 (2-5, .82)	4.35 (2-5, .76)	.047
Q5: I can assist family members and others through the grieving process.	3.76 (1-5, 1.01)	3.94 (1-5, .92)	.229
Q6: I am able to document the needs and interventions of my patients.	4.16 (1-5, .99)	4.00 (2-5, .92)	.314
Q7: I am comfortable talking with other health care professionals about the care of dying patients.	4.29 (2-5, .78)	4.19 (2-5, .77)	.374
Q8: I am comfortable helping to resolve difficult family conflicts about end-of-life care.	4.00 (1-5, .80)	4.00 (1-5, .97)	.162
Q9: I can recognize impending death (physical changes).	3.87 (2-5, 1.12)	4.09 (2-5, .91)	.165
Q10: I know how to use non-drug therapies in the management of patients' symptoms.	3.22 (1-5, 1.14)	4.08 (1-5, 1.06)	<.001
Q11: I am able to help alleviate patients' and family members' fears of getting addicted to pain medications.	3.13 (1-5, 1.28)	3.77 (1-5, 1.41)	<.001
Q12: I encourage patients and families to complete advance care planning.	4.08 (2-5, .88)	4.16 (1-5, .87)	.598
Q13: I am comfortable dealing with ethical issues related to end-of-life/ hospice/ palliative care.	3.86 (2-5, .88)	3.98 (2-5, .96)	.411

CNAs	Pre-Test Mean (Range, SD)	Post-Test Mean (Range, SD)	<i>p</i> -value
Q14: I am able to deal with my feelings related to working with dying patients.	3.61 (2-5, 1.07)	3.86 (2-5, .88)	.096
Q15: I am able to be present with dying patients.	4.19 (1-5, 1.03)	4.36 (2-5, .71)	.162
Q16: I can address spiritual issues with patients and their families.	3.94 (2-5, .98)	4.02 (2-5, .94)	.569
Q17: I am comfortable dealing with patients' and families' religious and cultural perspectives.	4.21 (1-5, .87)	4.33 (2-5, .73)	.261
Q18: I am comfortable providing grief counseling for families.	3.52 (1-5, 1.16)	3.84 (1-5, .95)	.059
Q19: I am comfortable providing grief counseling for staff.	3.36 (1-5, 1.27)	3.78 (1-5, 1.05)	.017
Q20: I am knowledgeable about cultural factors influencing end-of-life care.	3.65 (1-5, 1.03)	3.79 (1-5, 1.05)	.411
Q21: I can recognize when patients are appropriate for hospice.	3.59 (1-5, .98)	4.08 (1-5, .84)	.002
Q22: I am familiar with palliative care principles and national guidelines.	3.40 (1-5, 1.01)	3.92 (1-5, .88)	.003
Q23: I am effective at helping patients and families navigate with health care system.	3.98 (1-5, .87)	4.30 (2-5, .75)	.007
Q24: I am familiar with the services hospice provides.	2.92 (1-5, 1.21)	3.37 (1-5, 1.31)	.008
Q25: I am effective at helping to maintain continuity of care for dying patients.	3.58 (1-5, 1.05)	3.90 (1-5, .89)	.046
Q26: I feel confident discussing assisted suicide with patients and families.	3.62 (1-5, .96)	3.72 (1-5, .94)	.506
Q27: I have personal resources to help meet my needs when working with dying patients and their families.	4.10 (1-5, .91)	4.36 (1-5, .63)	.046
Q28: I feel that my workplace provides resources to support staff who care for dying patients.	4.00 (1-5, 1.10)	4.00 (1-5, 1.07)	1.000

Results Specific to the POLST Form Completeness

The quality metrics related to the POLST form completeness showed improvement with the PC education (52% pre-education versus 62% post-education; a 10% percentage point increase in form completeness). The range for items completed on any single POLST form was 1-31. The metric evaluating POLST completion did not change over time as there were no forms with completed data (0/30 for both pre-and-post-interventions).

POLST Form Items:

1. Pre-Intervention: 501 POLST Items Completed / Total POLST Items (501/960 → 52%)
2. Post-Intervention: 590 POLST Items Completed / Total POSLT Items (590/969 → 62%)

Figure 2. Pre-post educational intervention: Completed POLST form items

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the DNP project was to improve ACP by nurses in a large post-acute/ SNF located in Southern California. An essential tenet of ACP is to identify patient preferences including GoC/ treatment preferences and to document these in the patient's chart. The specific aims of the project were to describe current ACP documentation efforts, develop and implement a palliative and EoL care focused educational training program targeted at licensed and non-licensed nursing staff, and to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention on POLST documentation efforts. In the narrative to follow, the author addresses these specific aims sequentially.

Most previous work in developing ACP knowledge, skills and attitudes (KSA) has focused on physicians or other top tier providers. Yet bedside care providers, especially unlicensed CNAs, serve an essential role in late life care. These individuals spend more time with patients and families in their final days than any other professional or paraprofessional and thus have enormous potential to mitigate the suffering during this challenging time (Pesut & Greig, 2017). It is unfortunate that little attention has been paid to employing empiric approaches to improving care provided by these essential individuals (Head, Washington, & Myers, 2013). Thus, this project represents a unique opportunity to improve EoL skills for both licensed and non-licensed nursing staff.

There are a handful of studies and quality improvement (QI) projects that support the implementation of a PC-centered educational training program for both licensed nurses and non-licensed nursing assistants/ CNAs in post-acute, SNF, and long-term care settings (Ersek, Kraybill & Hansberry, 2000; Ersek, Grant, & Kraybill, 2005; Percival & Johnson, 2013; Leclerc et al., 2014; Wen et al., 2012). A recent and relevant example is

Malik and Chapman's (2017) pre-post-test QI project which looked at PC trainings for CNAs in long-term care settings and found that KSA and quality EoL care improved significantly with a focused educational intervention. A distinguishing factor with the current project are results that suggest that licensed nurses benefit from PC-centered trainings as much *if not more* than unlicensed staff. This points to the need for these types of training programs that target licensed nurses *and* non-licensed CNAs in the post-acute and long-term care setting.

Regarding current ACP and GoC documentation practices at the SNF, these were found to be sub-optimal. Completed POLST form items were low at baseline (pre-chart audit 501 out of a possible 960 items (52%; see Figure 2). Post-chart review showed a 10 percentage point improvement in items completed (post-chart audit 590 [62%]). There were no completed POSLT forms identified in the pre-post chart review samples (pre 0/30 [0%], post 0/30 [0%]). In other words, a POLST form was present in all audited charts, however these were either incomplete or lacked a signature or both. Possible reasons for the finding include nurses' lack of time or deficits in knowledge or confidence in completing the form in a timely manner (within the 72 hours of admission rule). Additionally the pre-audit, training, and post-audit occurred over a 6 week period which may have been too short a duration of accurately assess the effectiveness of the educational intervention. The author speculates that any improvements in ACP documentation may be due to nurses' increased sensitivity to PC principles and concepts rather than specific POLST form knowledge gleaned from the trainings. Furthermore, the author is left to question whether ACP and GoC documentation is a priority for the staff at the SNF.

Development and implementation of a PC-centered educational program for licensed nurses and non-licensed CNAs in a post-acute setting proffered multiple highlights, challenges and insights. One highlight was participant receptivity to PC principles and EoL conversations. This was evident for both groups, but particularly for the CNAs. By the end of each training session participants exhibited enthusiasm and an animated interest in the material. Many verbalized a desire for more PC trainings. Challenges included limited timeframes for the trainings, particularly for the non-licensed CNAs (30 minutes vs. one hour for the licensed RN/ LVN group) and were related to facility logistics. Additionally, CNA trainings were mandatory whereas trainings for the licensed group were voluntary. This may account for the higher numbers of CNAs in the sample ($n = 50$ for CNAs; $n = 36$ for RN/ LVNs). Although the curriculum was adjusted to accommodate the time differences, information exchanges and knowledge transfers were unavoidably truncated.

Evaluation and effectiveness of the educational intervention also posits notable observations and insights. While the baseline KSA scores were similar between groups (mean 3.71 for licensed nurses vs. mean 3.76 for non-licensed CNAs), the licensed nurses demonstrated greater gains in KSA than the unlicensed did (4.17 licensed vs. 3.90 non-licensed). Our findings suggest that in our sample of licensed nurses and non-licensed CNAs, both groups had a similar knowledge base with respect to basic PC principles. While the gains in KSA were greater for the licensed group (4.17 licensed vs. 3.90 unlicensed), and were significant ($t = 2.1, p = .043$), whether the statistical significance reflects an alpha error (Polit & Beck, 2017) is a point worth considering. Even with the limited training timeframe, the non-licensed group showed improvements in mean scores

that practically matched those of the licensed group. The clinical implication is that PC-centered trainings are needed for all levels of nursing in these settings.

Also interesting were pre-post-test score expectations. The author was surprised to find that baseline scores for CNAs were almost equal to the licensed group. Because CNAs are generally not supported by regular trainings in PC concepts, the assumption was that baseline scores would have been low and that the spread between pre- and post-test scores would have been wider, even with the limited timeframe of 30-minutes. Scores for the licensed groups were mostly as expected.

Equally interesting to the author was the finding that there were a number of participants with mean KSA scores that actually diminished with the educational program. In other words, 19 out of 86 participants' (22%) scores decreased over time. Decreases varied from -1.11 to -0.04 across groups and were minimal. However, 17/19 participants with decrements were CNAs. The author speculates that the intervention served to increase sensitivity for both groups but especially the CNA group to the nuanced nature of PC and this resulted in a portion of the mean scores to adjust downward. In future projects, more attention will be focused on understanding perceptions of participants who report lower confidence in PC and EoL care. Reflective awareness has been shown to increase confidence and receptivity to learning in various areas of nursing practice and may be especially useful in PC-focused educational interventions (Gillett, O'Neill, & Bloomfield, 2016).

There were a few specific items in the KSA surveys where the values diminished with the intervention (see Tables 4 & 5). For example, the licensed RN/ LVN group reported less comfort in dealing with ethical issues and EoL (question 13 of the KSA).

Although mean differences were small, they were statistically significant (4.1 [SD .75] vs. 3.8 [SD .91], $t = 2.1$, $p = .044$). However, it is counterintuitive to assume that the intervention was deleterious to nurses' understanding of palliative and EoL care. Similar to what was proposed above, the author speculates that participants were sensitized to the ethical implications of PC principles and this resulted in decrements post-intervention.

The author also examined the pattern of responses for items that demonstrated the greatest amount of improvement. KSA acquisition showed statistical significance in 10 of the 28 (36%) KSA items for both groups. Notably, question 22, which asks about familiarity of PC principles and national guidelines, showed some of the highest improvements for both groups in post-test mean scores (3.14 [SD .96] vs. 4.14 [SD .90], $t = -5.0$, $p < .001$ for RN/ LVNs and 3.40 [SD 1.0] vs. 3.92 [SD .88], $t = -3.2$, $p = .003$ for CNAs). This suggests that basic PC principles were successfully internalized as a result of the educational intervention.

Another interesting finding relates to question 23, which asks about effectiveness in helping patients and families navigate the healthcare system. Both licensed nurses and CNAs showed improvements in pre-post-test comparisons (licensed nurses 3.86 [2-5, SD .64] to 4.42 [3-5, SD .65], $t = -5.5$, $p < .001$ and CNAs 3.98 [1-5, SD .87] to 4.30 [2-5, SD .75], $t = -2.8$, $p = .007$). This is often an area of great concern and confusion for patients and families facing debilitating health challenges including EoL. Most observers in the area of training and education would easily accept the idea that increases in knowledge acquisition may also increase confidence levels. Today's pressing and complex health care delivery system demands the ability to interact and guide patients and families in this respect. The author posits that non-licensed CNAs, with the support

of regularly scheduled PC trainings, could be placed in a better position to increase the quality of care at EoL.

While POLST item completion scores increased post-intervention (from 52% pre-chart audit to 62% post-chart audit), it is important to note that the author's choice of POLST form completeness as an outcome measure for this DNP project may not have been sensitive to the educational intervention. The educational intervention was broad-based and provided only very basic knowledge in PC principles in a 30-minute-to-one-hour in-service format. While timely and accurate completion of the POLST was discussed as part of the intervention, the PC training program was not specifically focused on POLST completeness. Additionally, CNAs have a limited role in completing the POLST form. Nonetheless, CNAs frequently face questions from patients and families related to the items specified on the POLST form. The author again posits that any improvement in POLST completeness was likely related to increased awareness of ACP and PC principles rather than detailed POLST completion instruction or to a general Hawthorne effect (Polit & Beck, 2017) at the site of the project.

Finally, a brief reflection on what worked well and what did not in terms of the intervention is worth mention. The instructional piece referred to as the "Free Speech" exercise worked well. The activity was held at the end of each of the training sessions. A participant would voluntarily read from a randomly chosen prompt (question or statement) that was written on a 3x5 index card. An example of a prompt would be, "How do you like to be with dying patients?" Participants exhibited high levels of animation and enthusiasm when sharing reflections or personal stories related to caring for an EoL patient or a family member. Many of the anecdotes were rich and served as

part inspiration and part instruction directed at either themselves, their peers or both. What did not work well was the short timeframe for all groups, particularly the CNAs. Thirty minutes was not enough time to review basic PC concepts or EoL care fundamentals, or to engage in more than one very brief interactive activity.

Limitations

This quality improvement project has several limitations. The first is that the time for the educational intervention was short. However, the intervention was extremely well received by the participants and the facility administration. Secondly, the project was conducted at only one site. However, this was a large facility located in an urban setting with a diverse staff and patient population, which facilitates the ability to apply this approach to similar settings and populations. Thirdly, the outcomes measured may not truly reflect the process delivered. In other words, while the educational process was targeted at RNs, LVNs, and CNAs, POLST form completion is done by licensed nurses and social workers and not CNAs. However, the goal of the project was to improve ACP within the clinical context of the post-acute/ SNF setting, and this was successful.

Clinical Implications

Palliative care training among licensed nurses *and* non-licensed CNAs is important to improve late life experiences for post-acute/ SNF-based populations. Innovative approaches are needed to empower both groups to engage in conversations about EoL and goals of care. Future endeavors will need to optimize scarce resources related to time for professional development (e.g. increase the time allotment for PC trainings and develop and support “PC champions”). Cultural and language differences

among licensed nurses and non-licensed CNAs may also play a role in how PC principles are perceived, internalized, and ultimately operationalized and this must be addressed.

Conclusion

This QI project demonstrates the feasibility of developing, implementing and evaluating an educational intervention designed to improve KSA in licensed nursing and non-licensed CNA staff related to palliative and EoL care in a post-acute/ SNF-based setting. With the exploding population of aging Americans who will be spending their final days in these facilities, this work will only become more important. Finally, the question of what we can learn from surveying non-licensed CNAs using a validated instrument intended for licensed MDs, RNs, and SWs is a relevant and pressing issue. The contributions of CNAs to ACP and EoL care has received little empiric attention, yet no individual spends more time at the bedside than these undervalued colleagues.

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APPENDIX A

SAMPLE DATA ABSTRACTION TOOL

Pre-Post-Intervention Chart Audits (10-2017 thru 11-2017)

Yes = 1; No = 0

<u>Patient ID</u>	<u>Date Abstracted</u>	<u>Age</u>	<u>Gender</u>	<u>Ethnicity</u>	<u>Date of Admission</u>	<u>Admitting Diagnosis</u>	<u>POSLT in Chart?</u>	<u>Item #1</u>	<u>Item #2</u>	<u>Item #3</u>	<u>... Item #31</u>
1	09/27/17	74	f	AA	09/24/17	Fall s/p ORIF	1	0	0	0	1
2	09/27/17	71	f	AA	08/03/17	CVA	1	1	1	1	1
3	09/27/17	96	f	AA	09/06/17	CVA	1	1	1	0	0
4	10/02/17	79	m	Pakistani	09/24/17	CAD	1	0	1	1	0
5	10/08/17	90	f	Latina	09/25/17	Colitis	1	1	1	1	0
6	10/12/17	84	m	AA	09/25/17	General weakness	1	1	0	1	1
7	11/02/17	49	m	Caucasian	09/21/17	Trauma & TBI	1	1	1	1	1
8	11/06/17	84	m	Caucasian	09/07/17	Seizures & CVA Dehydration &	1	0	0	0	0
9	11/10/17	80	m	Jamaican	09/25/17	CKD4	1	1	1	1	1
10	11/14/17	73	f	Caucasian	09/26/17	Flu & Weakness	1	1	0	1	1

APPENDIX B

KNOWLEDGE SKILLS & ATTITUDES SURVEYS

Survey 1: Pre-Post for RN/ LVN

Q1.1 CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN DOCTORAL PROJECT

Advanced Care Planning in a Skilled Nursing Facility: A Quality Improvement Project

You are asked to participate in a Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project conducted by Dane Shoemaker, MSN, NP-C, from the School of Nursing, California State University, Long Beach. You are a possible participant in this project because you are involved in goals of care and end-of-life conversations with patients and families. You are also involved in advanced care planning documentation (ACP) activities, such as completion of the Provider Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST) form.

PURPOSE OF THE PROJECT

The purpose of this DNP quality improvement project is to improve ACP activities in a post-acute, Skilled Nursing Facility (SNF). The specific aims of the project are: 1) to describe ACP documentation; 2) to implement an education program targeted at nursing and nursing assistant staff to support these efforts; and 3) to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention on ACP documentation and staff knowledge and attitudes related to ACP.

PROCEDURES

If you volunteer to participate in this study you will complete a 38-item survey on ACP knowledge and attitudes via paper/pencil or online (pre-test survey). You will then engage in an interactive one-hour in-service educational course on ACP. Upon completion of the in-service, you will be asked to repeat the same survey (post-test survey). The training will be interactive with discussions. You may choose to participate or not in the discussions and you may refuse to answer any question asked of you.

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

It is believed that the risk of participation in the in-service educational course is minimal. However, completion of the survey may result in breach of confidentiality, emotional duress due to the sensitive nature of the survey questions, and coercion. Every effort will be made to mitigate these potential risks and discomforts.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO PARTICIPANTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

The benefits of participation to the individual are minimal but may include psychological well-being from providing information to improve the quality of care for patients, families, loved ones, and communities.

PAYMENT FOR PARTICIPATION

There is no payment for participation in this educational project. However, at each in-service a \$10 door prize will be provided to a random participant.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law. Completed forms will only be seen by research staff, and the information provided on the forms will be analyzed as a whole and not on an individual basis. In addition, all forms will be confidential (you will not put your name on the forms), but a personal identifier (ID number) will be used to track your responses. Your name will not appear on data collection forms except for the consent form. Computer files with information that can identify you will be password protected. Your name or other facts that might identify you will not appear when we present this study or publish its results. All the forms will be kept in a locked filing cabinet for three years, and only authorized project staff will have access. All data collected from the forms will be destroyed three years after the conclusion of the project.

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

You can choose whether to participate in this educational project or not. If you volunteer to be in the project, you may stop at any time without consequences. You may also refuse to answer any questions and still participate in the project.

RIGHTS OF PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this DNP doctoral project. If you have questions regarding your rights as a project participant, contact the Office of University Research, CSU Long Beach, 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840; Telephone: (562) 985-5314. Email: ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu.

IDENTIFICATION OF INVESTIGATORS

If you have any questions about the project, please feel free to contact Dane Shoemaker, MSN, NP-C, Principal Investigator, daneshoe@csu.fullerton.edu, phone (415) 515-4913 or Joy Goebel, RN, PhD, Professor and Project Chair, joy.goebel@csulb.edu, phone 562-985-1635.

CONSENT OF PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

I understand the procedures and conditions of my participation described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this educational project.

- I agree
- I do not agree

Signature:

Q2.1 For the purposes of analyzing the impact of the in-service, you will be asked to complete a pre- and post-survey evaluation. A survey identification code will be necessary to match your pre- and post-responses. Please enter the last 5 digits of your cell phone number.

Q2.2 What is your age?

Q2.3 What is your stated gender?

- Male
- Female
- Transgender
- Other: _____
- Decline to state

Q2.4 What is your ethnicity, origin or race?

- African American
- Asian/ Pacific Islander
- Filipino
- Hispanic/ Latino
- Native American
- White/ Caucasian
- Other _____
- Decline to state

Q2.5 What is your highest level of education? (If currently enrolled, please state the highest degree or certificate received to date.)

- High school graduate or GED equivalent
- Vocational training or certificate program
- Associate's degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree or higher
- Decline to state

Q2.6 How many years have you worked in the post-acute/ skilled nursing facility setting?

- Years worked _____
- Decline to state

Q2.7 Have you ever had basic advance care planning/ end-of-life training?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure
- Decline to state

Q2.8 Do you personally have an advanced care directive?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

Q2.9 Please select your job title/ licensure level

- Registered Nurse (RN)
- Licensed Vocational Nurse (LVN)

Q3.3 Effective Care Delivery (RN/ LVN)

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Decline to State
21. I can recognize when patients are appropriate for referral to hospice.	<input type="radio"/>					
22. I am familiar with palliative care principles and national guidelines.	<input type="radio"/>					
23. I am effective at helping patients and families navigate the health care system.	<input type="radio"/>					
24. I am familiar with the services hospice provides.	<input type="radio"/>					
25. I am effective at helping to maintain continuity across care settings.	<input type="radio"/>					
26. I feel confident addressing requests for assisted suicide.	<input type="radio"/>					
27. I have personal resources to help meet my needs when working with dying patients and their families.	<input type="radio"/>					
28. I feel that my workplace provides resources to support staff who care for dying patients.	<input type="radio"/>					

Q5.1 What do you hope to learn/ what did you learn from this in-service training in Palliative Care?

KNOWLEDGE SKILLS & ATTITUDES SURVEY

Survey 2: Pre-Post for CNAs

Q1.1 CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN DOCTORAL PROJECT

Advanced Care Planning in a Skilled Nursing Facility: A Quality Improvement Project

You are asked to participate in a Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project conducted by Dane Shoemaker, MSN, NP-C, from the School of Nursing, California State University, Long Beach. You are a possible participant in this project because you are involved in goals of care and end-of-life conversations with patients and families. You are also involved in advanced care planning documentation (ACP) activities, such as completion of the Provider Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST) form.

PURPOSE OF THE PROJECT

The purpose of this DNP quality improvement project is to improve ACP activities in a post-acute, Skilled Nursing Facility (SNF). The specific aims of the project are: 1) to describe ACP documentation; 2) to implement an education program targeted at nursing and nursing assistant staff to support these efforts; and 3) to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention on ACP documentation and staff knowledge and attitudes related to ACP.

PROCEDURES

If you volunteer to participate in this study you will complete a 38-item survey on ACP knowledge and attitudes via paper/pencil or online (pre-test survey). You will then engage in an interactive one-hour in-service educational course on ACP. Upon completion of the in-service, you will be asked to repeat the same survey (post-test survey). The training will be interactive with discussions. You may choose to participate or not in the discussions and you may refuse to answer any question asked of you.

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

It is believed that the risk of participation in the in-service educational course is minimal. However, completion of the survey may result in breach of confidentiality, emotional duress due to the sensitive nature of the survey questions, and coercion. Every effort will be made to mitigate these potential risks and discomforts.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO PARTICIPANTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

The benefits of participation to the individual are minimal but may include psychological well-being from providing information to improve the quality of care for patients, families, loved ones, and communities.

PAYMENT FOR PARTICIPATION

There is no payment for participation in this educational project. However, at each in-service a \$10 door prize will be provided to a random participant.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law. Completed forms will only be seen by research staff, and the information provided on the forms will be analyzed as a whole and not on an individual basis. In addition, all forms will be confidential (you will not put your

name on the forms), but a personal identifier (ID number) will be used to track your responses. Your name will not appear on data collection forms except for the consent form. Computer files with information that can identify you will be password protected. Your name or other facts that might identify you will not appear when we present this study or publish its results. All the forms will be kept in a locked filing cabinet for three years, and only authorized project staff will have access. All data collected from the forms will be destroyed three years after the conclusion of the project.

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

You can choose whether to participate in this educational project or not. If you volunteer to be in the project, you may stop at any time without consequences. You may also refuse to answer any questions and still participate in the project.

RIGHTS OF PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this DNP doctoral project. If you have questions regarding your rights as a project participant, contact the Office of University Research, CSU Long Beach, 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840; Telephone: (562) 985-5314. Email: ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu.

IDENTIFICATION OF INVESTIGATORS

If you have any questions about the project, please feel free to contact Dane Shoemaker, MSN, NP-C, Principal Investigator, daneshoe@csu.fullerton.edu, phone (415) 515-4913 or Joy Goebel, RN, PhD, Professor and Project Chair, joy.goebel@csulb.edu, phone 562-985-1635.

CONSENT OF PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

I understand the procedures and conditions of my participation described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this educational project.

- I agree
- I do not agree

Signature:

Q2.1 For the purposes of analyzing the impact of the in-service, you will be asked to complete a pre- and post-survey evaluation. A survey identification code will be necessary to match your pre- and post-responses. Please enter the last 5 digits of your cell phone number.

Q2.2 What is your age?

Q2.3 What is your stated gender?

- Male
- Female
- Transgender
- Other: _____
- Decline to state

Q2.4 What is your ethnicity, origin or race?

- African American
- Asian/ Pacific Islander
- Filipino
- Hispanic/ Latino
- Native American
- White/ Caucasian
- Other _____
- Decline to state

Q2.5 What is your highest level of education? (If currently enrolled, please state the highest degree or certificate received to date.)

- High school graduate or GED equivalent
- Vocational training or certificate program
- Associate's degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree or higher
- Decline to state

Q2.6 How many years have you worked in the post-acute/ skilled nursing facility setting?

- Years worked _____
- Decline to state

Q2.7 Have you ever had basic advance care planning/ end-of-life training?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure
- Decline to state

Q2.8 Do you personally have an advanced care directive?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

Q2.9 Please confirm your job title

- Yes, I am a Clinical Nursing Assistant (CNA)

Q4.3 Effective Care Delivery (CNA)

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Decline to State
*21. I can recognize when patients are appropriate for hospice.	<input type="radio"/>					
22. I am familiar with palliative care principles and national guidelines.	<input type="radio"/>					
23. I am effective at helping patients and families navigate the health care system.	<input type="radio"/>					
24. I am familiar with the services hospice provides.	<input type="radio"/>					
*25. I am effective at helping to maintain continuity of care for dying patients.	<input type="radio"/>					
26. I feel confident discussing assisted suicide with patients and families.	<input type="radio"/>					
27. I have personal resources to help meet my needs when working with dying patients and their families.	<input type="radio"/>					
*28. I feel that my workplace provides resources to support staff who care for dying patients.	<input type="radio"/>					

Q5.1 What do you hope to learn/ did you learn from this in-service training in Palliative Care?

*Denotes changed question as compared to Survey 1 for RN/ LVNs

APPENDIX C
FACILITY LETTER OF SUPPORT

SUNNYSIDE
Nursing Center

June 14, 2017

Institute Review Board
California State University Long Beach
1250 Bellflower Blvd.
Long Beach, CA 90840-0301

Dear Institute Review Board,

This letter is written in support of the research study, *Advance Care Planning in a Skilled Nursing Facility: A Quality Improvement Project* by Dane Shoemaker, NP-C, California State University Long Beach. The topic of *Advanced Care Planning* has been seriously neglected in the post-acute setting. Sunnyside Nursing Center supports Mr. Shoemaker's project and believes in its potential to improve the quality of care for individuals and families facing serious illness. Sunnyside Nursing Center has 299 skilled Medicare certified beds with a staff of over 226 nurses. We encourage projects such as Mr. Shoemaker's that will increase the competency of the staff in ACP.

We will provide a space for his staff in-services, post announcements throughout the facility, and provide other administrative support as needed. We encourage him to administer pre-test post-test surveys to evaluate changes in knowledge and attitudes towards ACP in our staff. In addition, Mr. Shoemaker will review random samples of patient charts for ACP activities prior to and after his in-services to evaluate the effectiveness of the trainings on ACP practices.

We look forward to supporting Mr. Shoemaker in his Doctorate of Nursing Practice Project.

Sincerely,

Shane Dahl, NHA
Sunnyside Nursing Center

APPENDIX D**IRB APPROVAL**

On Oct 13, 2017, at 4:23 PM, Tiffany Rose <no-reply@irbnet.org> wrote:

Please note that California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has published the following Board Document on IRBNet:

Project Title: [1059542-2] ADVANCE CARE PLANNING IN A SKILLED NURSING FACILITY: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

Principal Investigator: Dane Shoemaker, MSN

Submission Type: Amendment/Modification

Date Submitted: October 10, 2017

Document Type: Approval Letter

Document Description: Approval Letter

Publish Date: October 13, 2017

Should you have any questions you may contact Tiffany Rose at tiffany.rose@csulb.edu.

Thank you,
The IRBNet Support Team

www.irbnet.org